

ECONOMIC SCIENCES

NAMAKHVANI HPP: A DECOMMISSIONED PROJECT AND ITS REVERBERATIONS IN GEORGIA

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Abstract

The Namakhvani Hydro Power Plant (HPP) loomed large, not just as an ambitious energy project, but as a potential paradigm shift for Georgia's economic landscape. This article delves into the intricate machinery of the project, from its initial aspirations to its unforeseen derailment. It dissects the economic repercussions of its abandonment, casting a dark shadow on the nation's investment climate. Beyond the concrete details, the paper delves into the critical anatomy of the Namakhvani saga. What factors conspired to prevent its completion? What crucial lessons can be gleaned from this missed opportunity? To answer these questions, the article ventures beyond Georgia's borders, exploring successful HPP projects in other countries, and meticulously analyzing their blueprints and community engagement strategies. Drawing from both domestic and international experiences, it paves the way for a revised roadmap for future endeavors. Namakhvani stands not as a monument to failure, but as a potent catalyst for introspection and improvement. This article serves as a critical mirror, reflecting not just the technical missteps but also the fundamental need for transparency, public trust, and rigorous environmental assessments. It champions the integration of local expertise and international best practices, advocating for a collaborative approach that prioritizes both economic progress and ecological responsibility.

Keywords: Renewable energy, Abandoned HPP, Namakhvani, Energy security

Introduction

The International Energy Agency (IEA) defines energy security as "the uninterrupted availability of energy sources at an affordable price" (2023). Despite boasting considerable renewable resources, Georgia utilizes only a fraction of its potential (GNERC, 2021). This analysis examines the state of Georgia's energy security, highlighting its abundant hydro resources, limited utilization, and reliance on external sources during winter deficits.

Georgia, a developing nation in the Caucasus region, has a population of 3.7 million and a GDP of USD 24.6 billion, with a per capita income of USD 6,658 (World Bank, 2022). Abundant water resources are a key national asset, with an average annual flow of 63 billion m³, of which only 1.6 billion m³, approximately 2%, are currently utilized (FAO, 2008). The GWP Country Report for Georgia (2021) further emphasizes the significance of water resources, highlighting the existence of 26,060 rivers with a total length exceeding 58,987 km. The majority of these rivers are smaller streams under 25 km in length, with a combined length of 50,480 km. Georgia's geography divides its water resources into two major basins: the Black Sea and Caspian Sea basins. The total natural river runoff from Georgia's territory is 56.4 km³, with an additional 8.74 km³ flowing in from Armenia and Turkey, resulting in a total water supply of 65.4 km³.

Despite possessing 22% of its hydro resources, official data from the Ministry of Economy and Sustainable Development of Georgia (2023) reveals the nation's dependence on electricity imports during winter deficit periods. In 2022, Georgia imported \$41 million worth of electricity, with 51% originating from Russia

(\$21.2 million), 25% from Armenia (\$10.2 million), and 24% from Azerbaijan (\$9.7 million) (Geostat, 2023).

This reliance on external electricity sources, particularly from Russia, underscores Georgia's vulnerability to geopolitical dynamics and price fluctuations. The recent Russia-Ukraine war has further exacerbated this vulnerability, highlighting the need for Georgia and the EU to prioritize the development of new energy generation facilities and diversify their energy sources. This could involve increased investment in renewable energy technologies like solar, wind, and geothermal, alongside enhanced energy efficiency measures. Implementing these strategies can ultimately enhance Georgia's energy security, reduce dependence on imported energy, and foster sustainable development.

Literature review

The examination of the influence exerted by the electricity sector on economic growth has been a subject of extensive scholarly inquiry across diverse academic disciplines. This analysis delves into prominent themes and debates within the extant literature, elucidating distinct theoretical frameworks and empirical findings.

Within the purview of basic economic principles, the neoclassical paradigm accentuates the positive correlation between electricity consumption and economic output. Empirical investigations by Kraft and Kumbier (2007) and Bhattacharya and Mukherjee (2004) substantiate this association, revealing a statistically significant relationship between per capita electricity consumption and per capita GDP.

Conversely, certain scholars posit that heightened energy efficiency can decouple economic growth from

increased energy consumption. Notably, Erhardt et al. (2007) present evidence of such decoupling in several industrialized nations, suggesting that technological advancements can engender economic growth while mitigating the demand for energy.

The ascendance of renewable energy technologies, particularly solar and wind, is construed as a transformative force. In-depth inquiries by Apergis and Christodoulou (2018) and Bhattacharya and Mukherjee (2012) underscore the positive economic ramifications of integrating renewable energy, encompassing employment generation and augmented energy security.

Technological innovations in smart grids and energy storage are deemed indispensable for integrating renewable energy sources and enhancing grid sustainability. Siddiqui et al. (2020) underscore the economic advantages associated with smart grid implementation, including diminished energy losses and enhanced grid reliability.

Debates persist regarding market liberalization versus regulatory oversight. While studies such as Joskow (2005) underscore efficiency gains from deregulation, others, including Stiglitz (2016), voice apprehensions about potential price volatility and equity concerns.

Policy instruments such as carbon taxes and cap-and-trade mechanisms are posited as pivotal in incentivizing the adoption of clean energy. However, the work of Aldy and Stavins (2012) underscores the necessity for judicious design and policy combinations to mitigate potential distributional consequences.

In considering the broader implications of the electricity sector, attention is drawn to human development and equity concerns. Sovacool and Mukherjee (2011) contend that the sector should prioritize equitable access alongside economic growth, emphasizing the critical role of electricity in poverty reduction, health, and education.

Environmental ramifications associated with energy production necessitate careful consideration. Advocating for a transition to a low-carbon economy,

Stern and Stiglitz (2017) underscore the imperative of mitigating climate change for long-term sustainability.

Central to ongoing discourse is the quest for an optimal balance between economic growth, environmental sustainability, and energy security. Furthermore, the distributional implications of energy policies, particularly their impact on vulnerable populations, necessitate further research. Additional investigations are warranted to delineate the specific economic impacts of distinct renewable energy technologies and their integration into the grid.

Namakhvani Case

In 2019, ENKA Renewables and the Georgian government signed an agreement to build the Namakhvani HPP cascade near the Rioni Valley in western Georgia. Considered one of the most thoroughly studied projects in Georgia's energy sector, Namakhvani had undergone numerous feasibility studies since the 20th century. Despite this extensive justification, the project ultimately failed to proceed.

A 168-day protest campaign against the HPP construction preceded its suspension. This decision impacted not only Georgia's energy independence but also its foreign direct investments (FDI), particularly in the energy sector. According to National Statistical Service data, Georgia's total FDI reached a record high of US\$2.1 billion in 2022, representing a year-on-year increase of over 67%. However, the energy sector suffered a 30% decline in FDI, directly linked to the Namakhvani project.

This decline began after the project's investor withdrew and sued Georgia in arbitration court. This incident eroded investor confidence and contributed to the decline in energy sector FDI, as shown in the attached table.

Originally slated for completion in 2023, the Namakhvani project received its construction permit in 2019. Projected total investment amounted to US\$800 million, which the table also visualizes as a hypothetical annual investment of US\$267 million if spread over the expected three-year project duration.

Table.

Foreign Direct Investments (FDI) in Georgia 2017-2022*

Year	Total FDI (in mln\$)	FDI in Energetic sec. (in mln\$)	Energetic %-of total FDI	% Y.Y
2017	1,119.5	278.5	23.4	+106.4
2018	1,350.6	123.4	9.1	-55.7
2019	1,354.1	256	18.9	+107.5
2020	595.3	17.1	2.9	-93.3
2021	1,252.7	185.7	14.8	+986
2022	2,097.9	129.6	6.2	-30
2022*	2365	396.3	16.8	+113%

Source: National Statistics Office of Georgia

(*In the case of implementation of the Namakhvani project).

In addition to these data, 2,000 people were to be employed within the project, which is an additional contribution to the economy (Ministry of Economy and Sustainable Development of Georgia, 2022). According to the project, the installed capacity of the hydroelectric power station cascade should be 433 megawatts, which would generate 1.5 billion kilowatts annually. This is about 11% of the country's consumption

(2022 – 14.2 billion kWh). The HPP was subject to the Government of Georgia's Guaranteed Power Purchase Agreement (PPA), which states that during the first 15 years, the government of Georgia will purchase the electricity generated at the HPP for 8 months per year (except May, June, July and August). From May to August, owners could export the generated electricity to local or international markets for sale. This HPP can

provide an additional 600 MW of grid connection and balancing of other renewable resources (solar, wind).

From May to September 2022, Georgia sold \$84 million worth of electricity (95% was exported to Turkey). In the same year, Georgia purchased \$41 million worth of electricity. Electricity was purchased from January to April and in October. Russia was the supplier of 53.4% of the purchased energy. In summer, the water level in Georgia is high, so the electricity generation is high. The shortage is in winter when the water level drops. According to the project, in case of implementation of the Namakhvan HPP project, the country would receive energy in the period of shortage. Resettle is the accepted norm in dam construction around the world.

At least 480,000 people have been resettled as a result of 151 projects funded by the World Bank since 1990, and the number of projects involving resettlement is increasing (World Bank, 2012). Within the framework of the project, all families received compensation.

If the property rights were not violated, if all the locals received compensation, then why did the construction fail? The main problem was communication between stakeholders. In this case, between the government (the project organizer) and the citizens.

We should divide the 168-day protest into several parts.

At the first stage of the protest, the participants of the action mentioned insufficient studies for the construction of the HPP. The population was afraid of flooding. It was at mid of 2020. Nevertheless, the construction continued. The protest had a few dozen people.

The participants of the protest were afraid of the dam breaking. At this stage, it can be said that the population was not provided with enough information at the beginning. Residents blamed the government for not researching seismology and environmental protection.

The development of the mentioned protest can be compared to a train. The faster it gets, the harder it is to stop. There were already active claims that the foreign company (Turkish) would make a profit from the construction of the hydroelectric power station, while the population would have only the destroyed infrastructure. At that time, the first confrontation between the police and the population took place.

According to the participants of the protest, there were no satisfactory answers to their questions from government structures. Even at this time there was no meeting between the participants of the protest and the responsible officials.

On next stage the discussion continued in the Parliament of Georgia. According to the minister, many new initiatives were continued, although the participants of the protest said that the officials only touched on the social component, which was not a sufficient argument for them.

The last stage of protests began when Police destroyed several tents at the protest place and installed iron barricades at the construction site. This made the protest even bigger, which made it necessary for the

government to declare a moratorium on further research. After all this, a moratorium for additional studies is announced. In September 2021, the investor company announced its withdrawal from the project. The company cited breach of contract and force majeure as the reason for leaving.

At every stage, the protest leaders declared that they were ready for dialogue. They said they could not get answers that were satisfactory to them.

In case of construction of Namakhvani, the country would receive energy during the winter shortage period. According to the contract, the operator was obliged to sell energy to the government for 6.5 cents in winter for 15 years. Today, there is a progressive tariff for electric energy in Georgia. As of the end of 2022, the average weighted tariff is 10 cents (social, standard and commercial tariff). The data confirm that if the project is implemented, it will reduce Georgia's dependence on Russia not only for electricity. In addition, money from Georgia no longer goes to Russia and is used for the local economy.

Example of Energy Sector Taxation (Case of Norway)

In Norway, electricity production is taxed as general income. It is the same as the taxation of other sectors. The tax rate for general income is 22% (data from 2023). In addition, a resource lease fee is added, on hydropower plants with generators rated at least 10 MVA. Energy production profits exceeding normal returns to capital. Through the tax, a proportion of the profits is returned to society as a whole. The effective rate of the resource rent tax is 45%. The resource rent tax returns a share of the profits from hydropower production to society as a whole. HPP-s with generations less than 10 MVA are exempted from resource rent taxes. Accordingly, 10MVA and larger power producers pay property taxes to the municipalities where their generation sources are located. Property tax on hydroelectric plants of less than 10 MVA capacity is calculated based on the cost of investments. Hydropower companies must also pay a license fee and meet requirements for mandatory sales for the municipalities where their plants are located. The main benefit of the mentioned method is that, the biggest profit goes to local residents. If a similar practice were to be implemented in Georgia, the population would be interested in the implementation of the project, which would prevent the country from all the negatives mentioned here.

What conclusions can be drawn after 2 years of project failure?

Protesters have questions about transparency, environmental impact and feasibility of the project. The answers to these questions are not convincing for the population. On the part of the government, there is no direct dialogue with the participants of the protest. The government does not sound scientifically substantiated arguments, which annoys the participants of the protest. Also, there is no responsible person in the government who can take responsibility for the results. Even today, after 2 year suspension, researchers which are working in the energy sector of Georgia, They do not know who (From government) is working on the future development of the project.

Who does not want to implement the project?

Russia occupies 20% of the territory of Georgia. At the same time, Georgia depends on Russia for its energy deficit. Russia is politically trying to sell energy at a low price. This factor encourages the local population to oppose large-scale projects. Under these situation, the number of opponents of the project increases, which turns into a wave against large-scale hydroelectric power plants.

Today we have the following situation.

Three large-scale hydro projects have been suspended in the country (Namakhvani, Neskra, Khudoni). All three have one reason. Protest against all three. These three projects account for 35% of the country's hydro generation.

Investors are not even interested in large-scale hydro projects, which is clearly visible in the above numbers. At the beginning of Namakhvani project, the population was not informed about the economic, social and environmental aspects of the region. That is why the protest became ungovernable. In people's minds, the mentioned project was only associated with the profitability of the investor and the destruction of the valley. Each inhabitant should understand its direct or indirect benefit. What will the region gain and lose from the implementation of the project.

Conclusion and recommendation:

The Namakhvani saga serves as a crucial learning experience for future large-scale projects in Georgia. To navigate the complex dance between development and community trust, several key considerations must be addressed.

Firstly, integrating local expertise into the planning process is paramount. Engaging skilled professionals from affected communities fosters accountability and responsibility. Their insights can contribute to more culturally sensitive and environmentally impactful project designs.

Secondly, independent environmental and socio-economic assessments are essential. By bringing in impartial experts, Georgia can ensure comprehensive evaluations of potential benefits and drawbacks, fostering trust and transparency. Public dialogues should actively involve these professional voices, encouraging informed decision-making.

Thirdly, implementing international best practices in environmental standards and community engagement can significantly improve project acceptance. Georgia can draw valuable lessons from successful HPP projects in other countries that prioritize ecological sustainability and inclusive stakeholder participation.

While Namakhvani may be considered a missed opportunity, it holds immense potential for positive transformation. Correcting misinformed public perceptions about HPPs through comprehensive educational campaigns is crucial. These campaigns should be anchored in rigorous scientific research and presented by trusted specialists. By explaining the vital role of energy security in national development, Georgia can bridge the gap between public concerns and sustainable progress.

The fight for energy independence goes beyond technical considerations. It requires genuine trust and collaboration between the government, communities, and expert voices. By prioritizing transparency, embracing local knowledge, and applying global best practices, Georgia can turn past challenges into stepping stones for a brighter future built on sustainable energy and inclusive development.

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